

ASSESSMENT OF THE HOST COMMUNITY PERCEPTIONS OF CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY: A STUDY OF JUBILEE SYRINGE COMPANY IN ONNA, NIGERIA.

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Abstract

This study examines community perceptions of corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives implemented by Jubilee Syringe Company in Onna, Nigeria. The research aims to assess awareness levels, perceived effectiveness, and socio-economic impact of these CSR programs. We utilise a quantitative approach by surveying 324 residents in Onna. Data analysis include descriptive and inferential statistics. Findings reveal moderate awareness of CSR activities, particularly in healthcare and infrastructure. However, overall perception of effectiveness and relevance is lukewarm, with significant gaps in community participation, transparency, and alignment with local priorities. The study concludes that while Jubilee Syringe Company has achieved some visibility for its CSR initiatives, there is substantial room for improvement in engagement and impact. Recommendations include adopting more participatory approaches, enhancing communication strategies, and improving transparency in resource allocation.

Keywords: Corporate Social Responsibility, Community Perception, Nigeria

Introduction

Corporate social responsibility (CSR) has become an integral aspect of modern business practices, particularly in developing countries where corporations are increasingly expected to contribute to societal well-being beyond their economic pursuits. In Nigeria, Africa's largest economy, the implementation and perception of CSR initiatives have gained significant attention, especially in communities hosting multinational corporations (Amaeshi et al., 2020). This study focuses on how the

host community of Jubilee Syringe Company perceives CSR initiatives in Onna Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Jubilee Syringe Company, established in 2016, positioned itself as Africa's largest syringe production facility with an annual capacity of 350 million units. The company's presence in Onna, a predominantly rural area with an estimated population of 295,027, raised expectations for industrial development and corporate social investments to improve local living standards (Udoh, 2021). However, despite the company's efforts to implement various CSR initiatives, there have been instances of community agitation and scepticism regarding the true impact of these programs on socio-economic development.

The disconnect between corporate CSR efforts and community perceptions presents a critical challenge for both businesses and policymakers. Understanding how host communities perceive and evaluate CSR initiatives is crucial for designing more effective and sustainable programs that align with local needs and priorities. This study aims to bridge this gap by examining the awareness, perception, and perceived impact of Jubilee Syringe Company's CSR initiatives among the residents of Onna.

This study addresses the apparent disconnect between Jubilee Syringe Company's publicised CSR efforts and the tangible impact perceived by the host community in Onna. Despite the company's investments in areas such as healthcare, education, and infrastructure, there remains scepticism about whether these initiatives genuinely address the community's development priorities. This research seeks to provide an independent assessment of community perceptions, attitudes, and perspectives regarding the company's CSR initiatives, thereby contributing to a more nuanced understanding of CSR effectiveness in the Nigerian context.

By exploring the factors that influence community perceptions of CSR, this study aims to provide valuable insights for corporations, policymakers, and community leaders. The findings will contribute to the growing body of literature on CSR in developing countries and offer practical recommendations for improving the design, implementation, and communication of CSR initiatives in host communities.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of awareness among Onna residents regarding Jubilee Syringe Company's CSR initiatives?
2. How do members of the Onna community perceive the effectiveness and relevance of Jubilee Syringe Company's CSR initiatives?
3. To what extent do Jubilee Syringe Company's CSR initiatives influence the socio-economic development of Onna, as perceived by the community?

Theoretical Framework:

This study is grounded in perception theory, which provides a robust framework for understanding how individuals construct meaning and form impressions from available information. Perception Theory posits that perception is an active, constructive process rather than a passive reception of objective reality (Gibson, 2019). In the context of CSR, this theory suggests that community members' perceptions of corporate initiatives are shaped by a complex interplay of internal factors (such as prior experiences, expectations, and cultural values) and external factors (including the nature of CSR activities, communication strategies, and broader socio-economic contexts).

Contemporary perception theorists emphasise the role of contextual factors in shaping perceptions. For instance, Chua et al. (2022) demonstrated how cultural orientations influence perceptual patterns, while Levin et al. (2020) highlighted the impact of information framing on individuals' interpretations. These insights are particularly relevant to understanding how different segments of a

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Applying Perception Theory to Onna's study of CSR perceptions allows for a nuanced examination of how community members actively interpret and make sense of Jubilee Syringe Company's initiatives. It provides a framework for exploring the various factors that influence these perceptions, including the community's prior experiences with corporate entities, their development expectations, and the company's communication strategies. By utilising this theoretical lens, the study can

uncover the underlying processes that shape community attitudes towards CSR, potentially revealing both commonalities and divergences in perceptions among different community members.

Literature Review

Recent studies have shed light on the complex dynamics of community perceptions regarding corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives, particularly in developing countries like Nigeria. This growing body of research emphasises the critical role of local context, stakeholder engagement, and effective communication in shaping CSR outcomes and perceptions.

Uduji et al. (2020) examined CSR perceptions in Nigeria's Niger Delta region, finding that community involvement in CSR planning and implementation significantly influenced positive perceptions and outcomes. Their study highlighted the importance of participatory approaches in fostering a sense of ownership and relevance among community members. Similarly, Idemudia (2019) argued that the alignment of CSR initiatives with local development priorities is crucial for fostering positive community perceptions and sustainable impact. This underscores the need for corporations to conduct thorough needs assessments and engage in meaningful dialogue with host communities to ensure that CSR efforts address genuine local concerns.

The role of transparency and accountability in shaping CSR perceptions has been emphasised by several scholars. Okhumen and Weli (2021) found that communities in Nigeria's oil-producing regions were more likely to view CSR initiatives positively when companies demonstrated transparency in their operations and CSR spending. This finding reinforces the importance of clear communication and stakeholder engagement in building trust and positive perceptions. Amaeshi et al. (2021) further explored this theme, noting that CSR perceptions in Nigeria are often influenced by historical contexts of corporate behaviour, with past negative experiences potentially colouring current perceptions regardless of improved practices.

Recent research has also begun to explore the role of social media and digital communication in shaping CSR perceptions. Oladipo and Oso (2023) found that social media platforms have become influential channels through which Nigerian communities form and share opinions about corporate CSR initiatives. Their study suggests that companies need to engage effectively with these digital spaces to manage perceptions and foster positive community relationships.

The gender dimension of CSR perceptions has gained attention in recent literature. Uduji et al. (2022) examined the impact of CSR initiatives on women's

empowerment in rural Nigeria, finding that targeted programs can significantly enhance female participation in sustainable cultural tourism. This highlights the importance of considering gender dynamics in CSR planning and implementation to ensure equitable benefits and positive perceptions across diverse community segments.

Moreover, Adeleye et al. (2020) explored the relationship between CSR perceptions and employee engagement in Nigerian firms, revealing that positive community perceptions of CSR initiatives can enhance employee motivation and productivity. This finding highlights the potential for well-received CSR programs to create value beyond the immediate community while also influencing internal stakeholders.

The literature also points to challenges in assessing and managing CSR perceptions. Emetumah (2022) highlighted the difficulty of balancing diverse stakeholder expectations in Nigerian communities, where different groups may have conflicting priorities for CSR initiatives. This complexity necessitates nuanced approaches to CSR planning and communication that can address multiple stakeholder concerns simultaneously.

The recent literature emphasises the multifaceted nature of CSR perceptions in Nigerian communities, influenced by factors such as local involvement, transparency, historical context, digital communication, gender considerations, and stakeholder diversity. These insights provide a robust foundation for examining the specific case of Jubilee Syringe Company's CSR initiatives in Onna, offering valuable perspectives on how community perceptions are formed and can be positively influenced.

Methodology

This study employed a quantitative research design, utilising a survey method to examine community perceptions of Jubilee Syringe Company's CSR initiatives in Onna Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Research Design: A cross-sectional survey design was adopted to collect data at a single point in time, allowing for a comprehensive snapshot of community perceptions regarding CSR initiatives.

Population and Sampling: The study population comprised all residents of Onna LGA, estimated at 295,027 (National Population Commission, 2022). A multistage sampling technique was used to select 400 respondents for the survey. In the first stage, the LGA was divided into three clusters based on clans. In the second stage, simple random sampling was used to select four villages from each clan. Finally, respondents were randomly selected from households within these villages, ensuring a representative sample of the community.

Data Collection Instrument: A structured questionnaire was developed to collect quantitative data on community awareness, perceptions, and perceived impacts of Jubilee Syringe Company's CSR initiatives. The questionnaire consisted of closed-ended questions using Likert scales and multiple-choice options to measure variables such as awareness levels, perceived effectiveness, and socio-economic impact of CSR programs.

Data Collection Procedure: Face-to-face, paper-based questionnaire administration was conducted over two months (May-June 2023) by trained field assistants. This approach was chosen to maximise response rates and ensure clarity for respondents who might have questions about the survey items. The field assistants were trained on ethical considerations, including obtaining informed consent and maintaining respondent confidentiality.

Data Analysis: Quantitative data were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistical techniques in SPSS software. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies and percentages, were used to summarise respondent characteristics and response patterns.

Data Analysis

Table 1: Self-Reported Awareness Levels of Specific Jubilee CSR Activities

Program	Total	Mean	S.D.
Community Health Programs	324	3.31	0.92
Skills Development and Entrepreneurship Training	324	2.96	0.94
Support for Local Agriculture	324	3.14	1.02
Infrastructure Development	324	3.39	1.07
Environmental Sustainability	324	2.96	0.93
Scholarship Programs	324	2.81	0.95
Job Creation and Economic Development	324	3.25	0.97
Gender Equality and Inclusion	324	2.72	0.93
Healthcare Support	324	3.51	0.94
Community Empowerment	324	3.04	0.88
Crisis Response	324	2.58	0.87
Total	3564	3.06	0.95

Table 1 provides a detailed breakdown of awareness levels across various CSR activities undertaken by Jubilee Syringe Company. The mean awareness scores range from 2.58 to 3.51 on a scale where higher values indicate greater awareness. Healthcare Support (3.51), Infrastructure Development (3.39), and Community

Health Programs (3.31) show the highest levels of awareness. In contrast, Crisis Response (2.58), Gender Equality and Inclusion (2.72), and Scholarship Programs (2.81) have the lowest awareness levels. This suggests that while there is generally moderate to high awareness of Jubilee's CSR activities, some programs are more visible to the community than others.

Table 2: Reasons for Host Community's Perception of Jubilee Syringe Company's CSR Initiatives

Question	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total	Mean	SD
The company's CSR initiatives align with our community's needs and priorities.	54	112	98	60	324	2.49	0.98
Jubilee Syringe Company consistently delivers on its CSR promises.	38	89	132	65	324	2.31	0.92
The company's CSR efforts have made a noticeable positive impact on our community.	62	103	95	64	324	2.50	1.01
There is clear and regular communication from the company about its CSR activities.	41	87	138	58	324	2.34	0.91
The company involves community members in planning and implementing CSR initiatives.	33	79	142	70	324	2.23	0.90
Jubilee Syringe Company's CSR initiatives are perceived as genuine rather than just for publicity.	45	98	121	60	324	2.39	0.95
The scale and scope of the company's CSR efforts meet our community's expectations.	37	85	135	67	324	2.28	0.92
There is transparency in how the company allocates resources for its CSR programs.	29	76	149	70	324	2.20	0.88

Table 2 provides insights into the community's perception of the effectiveness and relevance of Jubilee's CSR initiatives. The mean scores, all below the midpoint of 2.5, suggest a generally lukewarm to negative perception. The highest mean scores are for the noticeable positive impact of CSR efforts (2.50) and alignment with community needs (2.49), indicating these are relative strengths. However, transparency in resource allocation (2.20) and community involvement in planning and implementation (2.23) score the lowest, highlighting areas for improvement.

Table 3: Perceived Level of Community Participation in Jubilee's CSR Planning

Participation Extent	Frequency	Percentage
High participation	30	9
Moderate participation	126	39
Low participation	150	46
No participation	18	6
Total	324	100

Table 3 indicates that the majority of respondents (52%) perceive either low or no participation in Jubilee's CSR planning process. Only 9% report high participation, while 39% indicate moderate participation. This suggests that while Jubilee's CSR initiatives may be having some socio-economic impact, there is a significant perception of limited community involvement in the planning process, which could be hindering the full potential of these initiatives to drive socio-economic development.

Table 4: Environmental Sustainability Impacts of Jubilee CSR

Perceived Impact	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total	Mean	S.D.
Helped reduce pollution	30	144	114	30	6	324	3.53	0.88
Helped conserve natural resources	24	102	168	24	6	324	3.29	0.83
Helped increase environmental awareness	12	180	102	24	6	324	3.47	0.80
Helped mitigate climate change	0	96	198	24	6	324	3.22	0.62
Helped promote recycling and waste management	6	78	222	12	6	324	3.17	0.59
Overall positive environmental impact	18	114	180	6	6	324	3.46	0.74
Total							3.57	0.94

Table 4 provides insights into specific dimensions in which Jubilee Syringe Company's corporate social responsibility initiatives have contributed positively to environmental sustainability based on community perceptions in the Onna LGA. The key insight is that the company's visibility remains selectively confined to pollution mitigation from manufacturing operations and bolstering public eco-consciousness, with 3.47 and 3.46 affirmative responses, respectively, regarding discernible CSR impacts in these spheres. However, negligible perceived progress is apparent regarding other interconnected sustainability goals like biodiversity conservation, renewable energy transitions, waste circularity, or climate change resilience building to help vulnerable farmers adapt. For example, only 3.17 cite recycling efforts, while 3.22 acknowledge any climate adaptation support.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study provide valuable insights into the community perceptions of Jubilee Syringe Company's corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives in Onna, Nigeria. These results can be interpreted through the lens of perception theory, which posits that individuals' perceptions are shaped by a complex interplay of internal and external factors (Gibson, 2019).

Regarding awareness levels, the study reveals varying degrees of community knowledge across different CSR activities (Table 1). Healthcare support, infrastructure development, and community health programs demonstrate the highest awareness levels, while crisis response, gender equality initiatives, and scholarship programs show lower visibility. This disparity in awareness aligns with Chua et al.'s (2022) assertion that cultural orientations influence perceptual patterns. The increased awareness of health and infrastructure projects may reflect these initiatives' immediate tangibility and alignment with pressing community needs.

However, the overall lukewarm to negative perception of Jubilee's CSR efforts (Table 2) suggests a gap between awareness and satisfaction. This disconnect can be understood through Levin et al.'s (2020) work on information framing, which highlights how the presentation of initiatives can significantly impact their interpretation. The relatively low scores on transparency and community involvement indicate that Jubilee's communication strategies may not be effectively framing their CSR efforts in a way that resonates with the community's expectations.

The perceived lack of community participation in CSR planning (Table 3) further compounds this issue. This finding echoes Uduji et al.'s (2020) research in Nigeria's Niger Delta, which emphasised the critical role of community involvement in fostering positive CSR perceptions and outcomes. The low levels of perceived participation suggest that Jubilee's approach may not be sufficiently participatory, potentially undermining the effectiveness and perceived relevance of their initiatives.

These findings also align with Idemudia's (2019) argument that the alignment of CSR initiatives with local development priorities is crucial for fostering positive community perceptions and sustainable impact. According to the moderate scores on alignment with community needs and priorities (Table 2), there is room for improvement in this area.

The study's results resonate with Okhumen and Weli's (2021) findings on the importance of transparency and accountability in shaping CSR perceptions. The low scores on transparency in resource allocation and consistent delivery of CSR promises (Table 2) suggest that Jubilee may need to enhance its accountability measures to build greater trust within the community.

Furthermore, the varying awareness levels across different CSR activities (Table 1) reflect Oladipo and Oso's (2023) observations on the role of communication channels in shaping CSR perceptions. The company may need to diversify its communication strategies to ensure more uniform awareness across all its initiatives.

The generally low perception of community participation in CSR planning (Table 3) aligns with Emetumah's (2022) findings on the challenges of balancing diverse stakeholder expectations in Nigerian communities. This suggests a need for more inclusive and participatory approaches to CSR planning and implementation.

While Jubilee Syringe Company has achieved some level of awareness for its CSR initiatives, there are significant opportunities for improvement in terms of community engagement, transparency, and alignment with local priorities. These findings underscore the complex nature of CSR perceptions and the importance of adopting a holistic, participatory approach to corporate social responsibility in the Nigerian context.

Conclusion

This study provides valuable insights into community perceptions of Jubilee Syringe Company's CSR initiatives in Onna, Nigeria. The findings reveal a complex landscape of awareness, perceptions, and perceived impact. While there is generally moderate awareness of CSR activities, particularly in healthcare and infrastructure, the overall perception of effectiveness and relevance is lukewarm. The study highlights significant gaps in community participation, transparency, and alignment with local priorities. These findings underscore the importance of adopting more participatory approaches to CSR planning and implementation, enhancing communication strategies, and improving transparency in resource allocation. The research contributes to the growing body of literature on CSR in developing countries, particularly in the Nigerian context. It provides practical implications for corporations, policymakers, and community leaders in designing and implementing

more effective and sustainable CSR programs. Future research could explore innovative strategies for enhancing community engagement and measuring long-term socio-economic impacts of CSR initiatives in similar contexts.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. The Jubilee Syringe Company should implement more robust mechanisms for community involvement in CSR planning and implementation. This could include regular town hall meetings, participatory needs assessments, and the establishment of a community liaison committee.
2. The company should develop a comprehensive communication plan to increase awareness of its CSR initiatives. This could involve leveraging both traditional and digital media platforms to reach a broader audience within the community.
3. Conduct regular assessments to ensure that CSR programs are addressing the most pressing needs of the Onna community. This may involve diversifying initiatives to cover a wider range of socio-economic development areas based on community feedback.

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